

Project Web Site

FRESH-D7.1-ProjectWebSite

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Version control sheet

WP	7. Communication and Dissemination
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1. Executive summary

This document, D7.1 Project Website, is a deliverable of the FRESH Project, which is funded by the European Union H2020 Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101069605. The document describes the motivation behind the concept of the website and the objectives as a key tool for dissemination and communication actions. The document provides a description of the content of the public site, defining also the social media tools used.

2. Purpose of the project website deliverable

The Project Website is the first deliverable of the WP7: Communication and Dissemination. The main purpose of this deliverable is to describe the key points of design, execution, content, use and the communication strategy behind the internet platform of the FRESH project. The URL of the website is www.iccom.cnr.it/horizon-eu-fresh and it has been online since beginning January 2023. The social media accounts of the project were created at the same time. Both the website and social media networks constitute key communication tools to increase project visibility and impact toward different audiences: Scientific community & specialized audiences; Industrial sector; Policy actors, Funding agencies and authorities; Citizens and the General public; R&I Networks; Media/Science Communication. They are also important tools for sharing information between FRESH partners.

3. Main objectives and responsibilities

The website directly contributes to the main objectives of the Dissemination and Communication Plan (D7.2), as a key dissemination and communication tool it will help to:

- Maximize the visibility of the project, raising awareness of its progress and results, and presenting the consortium members.
- Provide contents and regular updates adequate for the targeted audiences and establish regular analyses to increase their engagement and communication impact.
- Disseminate the activities and documents generated from all Work Packages during the lifetime of the initiative, contributing to promoting the project's results and to the Open Science concept.

The CNR is responsible for the development, updates and maintenance of the website and social media, as leader of WP7 Dissemination and communication. All consortium members are responsible for regularly contributing to the contents of the website and are engaged to support the FRESH website by disseminating it through their own websites and social media channels.

4. Website development and description

FRESH website is accessible at: www.iccom.cnr.it/horizon-eu-fresh. The platform has been created to serve as a key tool to support external communication and dissemination of the project objectives and results. The public website has been developed to act as an information hub for the project goals, participants, activities and results. The website has been designed following a responsive web design (RWD) to enable optimum visualization independently of the size of the screen (PC, tablet and mobile) or web browser one is viewing with and it will be updated frequently, as required, by CNR.

The website displays the following sections:

- **Home:** slide with main highlights, basic title and description of the project, highlights of the latest news and events, consortium information, newsletter subscribing form, access to the other web sections and to the project social networks (e.g. LinkedIn), information on EU funding and contact information.

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- **Project:** information about the project vision, including objectives, teamwork and a general planning structure.
- **Consortium:** list of all partner institutions taking part in the project, linking to a short descriptions and people involved in the team.
- **Outcomes:** outcomes generated through the project such as publications, presentations, graphic materials and videos, public deliverables and newsletters.
- **News & Events:** items of news regarding the project, interviews with experts, FRESH meetings, and related events.
- **Contacts:** contact form to reach the project team.

The Home page is designed to attract the attention of viewers by exposing the project logo and banner, listing the content of the website. It presents the project at a glance, highlighted news and events and consortium partners (Figure 1). All sections of the website have on top the FRESH logo and the menu bar enabling quick orientation through the search. All sections also provide, at the bottom, reference to Horizon Europe and European Commission (EC) support and links to social media and contact form to communicate to the project team.

Figure 1. FRESH project Home Page.

FRESH Data Management Plan (DMP) D7.4

The Project page provides a description of the project and the proposed technology, as well as an overview of the contributions and interaction of the consortium members, work package descriptions and a general planning scheme (Figure 2).

FRESH aims to contribute to reducing the European Union's dependence on fossil fuels for power generation, providing a cushion for the intermittent character of renewable electricity generation leading to stable, more predictable prices for renewable electricity, which is crucial for the future development of large-scale renewable power generation, and therefore, the energy transition. The project will achieve this through the development, construction and validation at TRL 4, of an integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate using an electrocatalytic process powered by renewable electricity. The highly stable potassium formate generated by the reactor will be stored safely for long periods (from short term or seasonal) in tanks. The subsequent conversion of the stored potassium formate to electricity on demand will use a direct Rankine system. The project includes development of the individual components (CO₂ to formate and formate to electricity), CO₂ sourcing and purification and ultimately the construction and validation of an integrated prototype at TRL 4.

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FRESH objectives

- 1. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 2. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 3. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 4. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 5. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 6. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 7. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 8. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 9. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate
- 10. Development of a fully integrated, cost-competitive process for conversion of CO₂ to potassium formate

Figure 2. Project description pages.

The Consortium page shows all partner logos (Figure 3) and after clicking on each one a short description of the institution appears with a link to the institutional websites, together with the pictures of the team members participating in the project (Figure 4).

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Figure 3. Consortium page.

Figure 4. Example of an inner partner page (CNR) as part of the Consortium page

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The Outcomes page will serve to make public the results and activities of the project, visitors could find the scientific articles published and other dissemination materials as presentations and posters. The newsletters generated through the project will also be available in this page, as well as public deliverables and other documents of interest.

The News and Events page (Figure 5) reports the main highlights of the project, for example notification of consortium meetings, partner participation in dissemination events, open job positions, etc.

Figure 5. Example of a post on News and Events Page

Finally, the website has its Contact page, where the visitors can leave a message by filling out the form. The message is directly sent to the e-mail address created for the project: fresh@iccom.cnr.it. For this contact form, a GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance form will display. In addition, as explained above, the bottom of each page has direct links to social media channels and a contact form to communicate to project team.

Regarding social media, there will be three active accounts on (LinkedIn, Twitter and Instagram): Currently, LinkedIn is active. Twitter and Instagram will follow.

- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/fresh-project-04744225b/> (Figure 7). It serves to promote the initiative among a specialized community. It emphasizes FRESH news and events, as well as other relevant items.

Figure 7. FRESH LinkedIn page.